
Beyond Borders and Bureaucracy: Enhancing International Arbitration for Construction Dispute Resolution in the Gulf Cooperation Council Construction Industry

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the use of international arbitration in resolving construction disputes within the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC), drawing on the author's doctoral research. Using a qualitative approach based on document analysis and expert interviews, it assesses procedural gaps, legal and administrative barriers, institutional challenges, international legal integration, and technological adoption in GCC arbitration systems.

The analysis shows that procedural inefficiencies particularly delays in arbitrator appointments and inconsistent timelines are the primary obstacles to effective arbitration. Legal and administrative barriers also hinder the consistent enforcement of arbitral awards across GCC jurisdictions. Although arbitration laws in the GCC are largely aligned with international standards such as the New York Convention and the UNCITRAL Model Law, differences in judicial interpretation and public policy application remain. Institutionally, arbitration centers exhibit uneven capacity, especially in case management and tribunal oversight, while the adoption of digital and AI-based tools is still limited.

The study recommends strengthening institutional capacity, enhancing judicial training, harmonizing procedures, and accelerating digital transformation to improve the efficiency and credibility of construction arbitration in the GCC.

1. Introduction

The Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC), comprising Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates (UAE), is a significant economic and geopolitical block.¹ The construction sector in the Gulf Cooperation Council has experienced rapid growth over the past twenty years, generating substantial demand for large and complex projects, and consequently leading to a significant rise in contractual disputes across the region.²

As a result of this rapid development, arbitration and other alternative dispute resolution mechanisms have emerged as the most suitable options for resolving construction disputes, due to their flexibility, neutrality, procedural efficiency, and the effectiveness of outcomes compared with traditional litigation.^{3 4}

Although the region has seen evident progress in both the construction sector and the development of international arbitration, several issues still limit the effectiveness of arbitration in the GCC. These include procedural gaps, uneven enforcement of arbitral awards, and differences in the institutional capacity of national judicial systems. There are also bureaucratic hurdles, delays in appointing arbitrators, and a slow pace in adopting technological tools that could make arbitration faster and more transparent. Together, these challenges affect the credibility of arbitration outcomes in a sector where disputes have a direct impact on project delivery,

financial exposure, and the relationships among stakeholders.^{5,6}

This study aims to examine the effectiveness of international arbitration in resolving construction disputes across the GCC region, with particular focus on procedural efficiency, legal and institutional challenges, and the role of international legal frameworks and digital transformation.

To achieve this aim, the study is guided by the following specific research objectives:

1.1 To examine procedural, legal, and institutional factors affecting the efficiency and enforcement of construction arbitration in GCC countries, including procedural gaps, administrative barriers, and institutional capacity.

1.2 To assess the integration of international arbitration law and technological tools within GCC arbitration systems, focusing on legal harmonization, judicial interpretation, and digital transformation.

Building on these objectives, this study presents a structured analysis of the main procedural, legal, institutional, and technological challenges affecting construction arbitration within the GCC. It further proposes recommendations aimed at supporting the development of a more efficient and innovation-driven regional framework for dispute resolution.

¹ Evelyn Devadason et al., 'Leveraging Trade Opportunities with Non-Traditional Partners: The Malaysia-GCC Perspective', *PSN: International Trade Policy* 27 (November 2011), <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1960470>.

² Tariq Umar, 'The Impact of COVID-19 on the GCC Construction Industry', *International Journal of Service Science, Management, Engineering, and Technology (IJSSMET)* 13, no. 2 (2022): 1-17, <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJSSMET.20220301.0a1>.

³ Kathleen M. J. Harmon, 'Resolution of Construction Disputes: A Review of Current Methodologies', *Leadership and Management in Engineering* 3, no. 4 (2003): 187-201, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1532-6748\(2003\)3:4\(187\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1532-6748(2003)3:4(187)).

⁴ Harmon, 'Resolution of Construction Disputes'.

⁵ Nazeem Ansary et al., 'Adjudication and Arbitration as a Technique in Resolving Construction Industry Disputes A Literature Review', 10 December 2017, 70-81, <https://doi.org/10.15224/978-1-63248-139-9-55>.

⁶ Amit Moza and Virendra Kumar Paul, 'Review of the Effectiveness of Arbitration', *Journal of Legal Affairs and Dispute Resolution in Engineering and Construction* 9, no. 1 (2017): 03716002, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)LA.1943-4170.0000204](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)LA.1943-4170.0000204).

2. Literature Review

The notable growth of arbitration in the construction sector over recent decades reflects global changes in how disputes are resolved and the increasing complexity of infrastructure projects in the GCC. The literature indicates that construction disputes frequently arise from project delays, changes in scope, rising costs, and ambiguous contract terms. These recurring issues have made arbitration the preferred method for resolving disputes in the construction industry.

The international practices reviewed highlight several essential elements such as neutrality, enforceability, confidentiality, and procedural flexibility. When these elements are present, arbitration becomes a more effective and suitable option than traditional litigation, whether the dispute involves domestic projects or large cross-border construction contracts. Central to these practices are global frameworks such as the New York Convention and the UNCITRAL Model Law, which provide predictable standards for recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards, ensuring coherence across jurisdictions participating in international commerce.⁷

A review of established arbitration models including those administered by the International Chamber of Commerce (ICC)⁸, London Court of International Arbitration (LCIA), Singapore International Arbitration Centre (SIAC)⁹, and the International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID)¹⁰ shows that modern arbitral institutions prioritize efficiency through streamlined procedures, institutional

oversight, and improved case management tools. These models have influenced GCC states as they sought to align their domestic arbitration systems with globally recognized standards.

The arbitration landscape in the GCC presents a system that blends international legal influences with local legislative characteristics rooted in civil law and Shari'ah principles. Although countries such as the UAE, Saudi Arabia, and Qatar have taken significant steps toward modernizing their arbitration laws and establishing specialized centers, noticeable differences remain in procedural rules, the level of judicial support, and institutional readiness. These variations result in uneven arbitration experiences across different countries, creating additional challenges for stakeholders involved in construction projects that span multiple GCC states.¹¹

The legal frameworks in the GCC reflect a combination of similarities and differences. On one hand, GCC states share a common commitment to international conventions and the modernization of their legislation. On the other hand, noticeable variations persist in administrative procedures, evidentiary rules, and judicial interpretation, all of which are shaped by the unique characteristics of each national legal system. Studies indicate that enhancing the effectiveness of arbitration in construction disputes across the region requires deeper steps toward harmonizing procedures, strengthening

⁷ Ifeoma Nwakoby and Chinwe Iloka, 'Recognition and Enforcement of International Commercial Arbitral Award: New York Convention in Focus', *International Journal of Comparative Law and Legal Philosophy* 4 (2022): 147.

⁸ Rhodes-Vivour San, *Recent Trends and Opportunities in International Commercial Arbitration*; Nwakoby and Iloka, 'Recognition and Enforcement of International Commercial Arbitral Award'.

⁹ SIAC, 'Administered Arbitration-Singapore International Arbitration Centre', *Singapore International Arbitration Centre*, n.d., accessed 26 June 2024, <https://siac.org.sg/administered-arbitration>.

¹⁰ Claudio Salas, 'Energy Arbitration in Latin America', 25 July 2019, <https://globalarbitrationreview.com/review/the-arbitration-review-of-the-americas/2020/article/energy-arbitration-in-latin-america>.

¹¹ Aceris Law, 'International Construction Arbitration in the Middle East', Aceris Law, 6 March 2021, <https://www.acerislaw.com/international-construction-arbitration-in-the-middle-east/>.

relevant institutions, and improving alignment with internationally recognized standards.

Overall, the effectiveness of arbitration depends on the interplay between international legal instruments, domestic legal procedures, the institutional maturity of arbitration bodies, and the management of expectations among parties involved in large-scale construction projects.

3. Methodology

The study employed a qualitative research design to understand the legal, procedural, and institutional factors that shape arbitration practices in construction disputes within the GCC countries. The research setting covers all six GCC states, with particular focus on jurisdictions where arbitration activity and legal reforms are most prominent, such as the United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia, and Qatar.

The study population consists of professionals working in arbitration, construction law, dispute resolution, and institutional governance. A purposive sampling method was employed to identify participants who could provide in-depth and valuable insights aligned with the study objectives, particularly those relating to procedural efficiency, legal and administrative barriers, institutional capacity, and the application of international arbitration frameworks within the GCC.

The final sample included arbitrators, academics, consultants, and legal practitioners, as these stakeholder groups are directly involved in the design, implementation, interpretation, and enforcement of arbitration procedures, and therefore represent the most relevant sources for achieving the study's research objectives.

The study relied on both primary and secondary data sources. Primary data were collected through semi-structured

interviews, which provided flexible opportunities to explore expert perspectives on procedural shortcomings, legal inconsistencies, and technological gaps in GCC arbitration. Secondary data included arbitration laws, institutional rules, international conventions, policy reports, academic literature, and comparative legal analyses related to construction disputes.

The study employed thematic analysis to interpret interview data and synthesize findings across various sources. Themes were developed inductively and aligned with the dissertation's objectives. This methodological approach was designed to develop a comprehensive understanding of arbitration practices in the GCC construction sector and to provide evidence-based insights that support policy recommendations and future reforms.

4. Findings and Discussion

Regarding the first objective (examining procedural gaps), the findings demonstrate that arbitration in construction disputes within the GCC has made progress toward international alignment; however, significant procedural inefficiencies persist. Expert interviews confirmed recurring delays in the appointment of arbitrators, a lack of clarity in procedural timelines, and inconsistencies in administrative case-handling processes across arbitration centers, which continue to hinder effective case management in large-scale projects.

With respect to the second objective (analyzing legal and administrative barriers), the legal analysis reveals that although GCC states have adopted modern arbitration laws inspired by the UNCITRAL Model Law, variations remain in judicial interpretation and enforcement practices. While some courts consistently support arbitration, others adopt more restrictive approaches, resulting in inconsistencies in the

recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards and creating legal uncertainty for contractors and investors.

In relation to the third objective (challenges of applying international arbitration law), the findings confirm that although GCC countries formally adhere to major international arbitration conventions and frameworks, practical application remains uneven due to divergent judicial interpretations, public policy considerations, and procedural traditions. This demonstrates a gap between formal international alignment and actual judicial practice.

Regarding the fourth objective (assessing institutional capacity), the findings reveal that institutional performance varies significantly among arbitration centers. Despite recent regulatory improvements, several centers continue to face shortages in specialized technical staff, weak internal case-management structures, and limited operational readiness for complex construction disputes. These shortcomings are particularly evident in tribunal appointment procedures and procedural supervision mechanisms.

Finally, regarding the fifth objective (technology and digital integration), the findings reveal uneven levels of technological adoption across GCC arbitration centers. While some institutions have introduced digital filing systems and limited online case-management tools, others continue to rely heavily on paper-based procedures, contributing to slower case registration, delayed document exchange, and reduced procedural transparency.

The findings confirm that arbitration in the GCC is supported by modern and generally well-developed legislation; however, its practical application remains uneven across jurisdictions. While GCC states have formally adopted international arbitration standards, procedural practice continues to differ

due to variations in institutional capacity and judicial interpretation.

The procedural delays identified especially in tribunal formation, unclear timelines, and inconsistent case-management practices reflect institutional capacity gaps rather than weaknesses in the legal framework itself. These inefficiencies directly affect the predictability of dispute resolution in large construction projects where time and financial risks are critical.

Differences in judicial interpretation and enforcement practices further contribute to legal uncertainty for parties operating across multiple GCC jurisdictions. Although legislation appears harmonized on paper, court practices still play a decisive role in shaping trust in arbitration outcomes.

Institutional capacity remains uneven among arbitration centers. While some institutions demonstrate advanced regulatory and professional capability, others continue to face limitations in staffing, internal systems, and operational readiness for complex construction disputes. This explains why legislative development has outpaced institutional maturity in parts of the region.

Technological adoption also varies significantly. Some centers have introduced digital filing systems and limited electronic tools, while others continue to rely on paper-based procedures, which slows case processing and reduces transparency. In parallel, the growing cost of arbitration continues to limit accessibility for small and medium-sized enterprises, reinforcing the perception that arbitration primarily serves large commercial actors.

Overall, the findings indicate that arbitration in the GCC is undergoing a transition from legislative modernization toward institutional consolidation. Achieving full maturity will require coordinated improvements in institutional performance,

judicial consistency, digital infrastructure, and procedural accessibility.

5. Implications to Existing Knowledge

5.1. *Shifting the focus from legislation to institutional performance*

Most previous studies have emphasized legal reforms and the adoption of international conventions. This study shows that the real effectiveness of arbitration depends more on institutional capacity, case management quality, and procedural organization than on legislation alone. This moves the discussion from what the law states to how it is applied in practice.

5.2. *Clarifying the role of Shari'ah principles in international arbitration*

Shari'ah is often presented as a barrier to arbitration. Still, this study demonstrates that its influence is limited and manageable, and that most challenges arise from procedural interpretation, not from fundamental incompatibility. This provides a more balanced understanding of the interaction between Shari'ah and international norms.

5.3. *Offering a broader understanding of arbitration efficiency*

Efficiency is not only about time and cost; it also encompasses other factors. The study expands the definition to include accessibility, technological readiness, institutional expertise, and stakeholder perceptions. This provides a more comprehensive framework that future research can adopt.

5.4. *Adding empirical insight into user perceptions*

While earlier research relied heavily on legal analysis, this study integrates expert interviews, revealing a clear gap between large companies and SMEs in their views and experiences of arbitration. This adds a realistic, user-centered perspective to the literature.

5.5. *Explaining how international standards are adapted in the GCC context*

The research reveals that GCC states apply international arbitration principles while also adapting them to local legal systems, resulting in a hybrid model. This enriches comparative legal scholarship and offers a valuable case for regions undergoing similar transitions.

5.6. *Highlighting the importance of institutional capacity-building*

Prior research challenges the assumption that modern laws automatically lead to effective practice. It demonstrates that training, administrative development, and organizational structure are essential for transforming legal reforms into tangible improvements.

5.7. *Contributing to the regional discussion on digital arbitration*

While global research on e-arbitration is expanding, work in the Arab region remains limited. This study provides new insights into technological, procedural, linguistic, and cybersecurity challenges facing digital transformation in GCC arbitration centers.

5.8. *Strengthening the academic case for regional harmonization*

The findings show how differences between GCC jurisdictions affect predictability, enforcement, and investor confidence. This supports the scholarly call for harmonization, backed by practical evidence from the field.

5.9. *Encouraging mixed qualitative-institutional methods in legal research*

The research demonstrates the value of combining doctrinal analysis with practitioner interviews, thereby promoting more empirical and practice-oriented legal research in the region.

6. Recommendations

6.1. *Strengthen Case Management Across Arbitration Centers*

Implement clear and enforceable timelines for tribunal formation, submission of pleadings, and scheduling of hearings to ensure a fair and efficient process. Establish

internal monitoring mechanisms to ensure procedural compliance, and require arbitrators to provide written justification for adjournments or delays.

6.2. Promote Harmonization of Arbitration Legislation Among GCC States

Launch a GCC-wide coordination initiative aimed at aligning procedural rules, enforcement standards, and interpretations of public policy. Encourage mutual recognition of arbitral awards to enhance predictability and reduce cross-border legal uncertainty.

6.3. Develop Training Programs for Judges and Arbitrators

Design continuous training modules focused on the New York Convention, the UNCITRAL Model Law, digital arbitration procedures, and the interaction between Shari'ah principles and international law. These programs may be delivered in partnership with universities and arbitration centers.

6.4. Improve Accessibility and Raise Awareness Among Stakeholders

Conduct bilingual awareness campaigns and publish simplified guides explaining arbitration procedures. Introduce fast-track or small-claims arbitration mechanisms to support SMEs, and adopt flexible fee structures to reduce financial barriers.

6.5. Integrate Digital and AI-Based Tools into Arbitration Processes

Expand the use of secure e-filing platforms, virtual hearings, and automated scheduling tools. Ensure that digital systems support both Arabic and English. Strengthen cybersecurity policies and organize regional training workshops to enhance digital competencies in arbitration practice.

6.6. Strengthen Institutional Capacity and Administrative Performance

Invest in the professional development of case managers, legal staff, and technical personnel to enhance their skills and capabilities. Standardize case-handling workflows and enhance institutional transparency by regularly reporting on caseloads, timelines, and performance indicators.

6.7. Establish a GCC Arbitration Knowledge and Research Network

Create a regional hub for sharing anonymized case data, research outputs, and best practices among arbitration centers and policymakers. Promote collaboration between academic institutions and arbitration bodies to support evidence-based reform.

6.8. Ensure Sustainable and Balanced Reform Efforts

Avoid overly frequent legislative amendments that may undermine legal stability. Focus instead on gradual, evidence-based improvements and enhance oversight mechanisms to evaluate the effectiveness of current frameworks.

6.9. Expand Academic and Professional Collaboration in Arbitration

Encourage universities and training institutions to develop specialized postgraduate programs in arbitration. Support joint workshops, academic forums, and policy roundtables to better align theoretical knowledge with institutional needs.

6.10. Advance Digital Transformation Through Regional Interoperability

Work towards developing compatible digital platforms across arbitration centers to enable seamless document exchange, shared databases, and unified digital standards. Such interoperability will enhance efficiency, reduce duplication, and strengthen confidence in electronic arbitration.

7. Recommendations for Further Research

The study emphasizes the need to expand future research on arbitration within the GCC, particularly by conducting quantitative studies that accurately measure case duration, associated costs, and procedural delays. Such empirical research would help establish clear benchmarks for assessing efficiency and systematically tracking the impact of reforms over time.

The study also emphasizes the importance of undertaking comparative judicial analyses of enforcement practices across GCC states, especially considering the differences identified in how public policy is interpreted and how foreign arbitral awards are recognized. Understanding the extent of convergence or divergence among judicial systems is essential for strengthening the coherence of the Gulf arbitration landscape.

Furthermore, the study highlights the need to examine the long-term effects of the legislative reforms introduced by several GCC countries. Longitudinal research is crucial for evaluating how these reforms impact investor confidence, procedural stability, and the consistency of enforcement in the years to come.

In the context of digital transformation, the study calls for a deeper investigation into electronic arbitration, focusing on the technological, linguistic, cultural, and security challenges facing GCC arbitration institutions. Comparative studies with leading global arbitration centers can also provide practical insights that may be adapted to the regional context.

From another perspective, the study emphasizes the importance of assessing arbitration awareness and literacy among small and medium-sized enterprises, and identifying financial, procedural, or informational barriers that may limit their participation especially given the observed gap between large companies and smaller firms in their approach to arbitration.

The study also recommends further exploration of the interaction between Shari'ah principles and international arbitration norms, to understand how contemporary judicial interpretations reconcile the two, and whether evolving jurisprudence is contributing to greater legal harmony across GCC courts.

At the institutional level, the study encourages the adoption of mixed-method research that combines legal analysis with organizational and behavioral studies to understand better how human resources, administrative structures, and internal processes influence arbitration outcomes particularly in light of the central role institutional performance plays in arbitration effectiveness.

Regionally, the study argues for examining potential models for legislative and procedural harmonization, including the feasibility of a unified GCC arbitration law, a shared enforcement framework, or common procedural standards, drawing on lessons from the other regional systems.

Ultimately, the study emphasizes the importance of evaluating capacity-building strategies for arbitrators, judges, and administrative staff, and of identifying best-practice training models that align with international standards. Strengthening these capacities is crucial for enhancing institutional performance and improving the overall quality of the arbitration environment in the region.

8. Limitations of the Study

The study relied on eight expert interviews, which is fewer than initially planned. Although the participants came from varied backgrounds arbitrators, academics, consultants, and practitioners the limited sample size may have narrowed the range of perspectives captured.

Interview representation was stronger in the United Arab Emirates and Saudi Arabia, while participation from Kuwait, Bahrain, and Oman was more limited. As a result, some country-specific details within the GCC may not be fully reflected in the findings.

The study was primarily based on qualitative interviews, supported by secondary sources. While this approach provided valuable depth and context, the absence of quantitative data

such as actual case durations or cost figures restricted the ability to measure arbitration efficiency with numerical accuracy.

Confidentiality rules applied by arbitration centers also limited access to case files, timelines, and enforcement records, which prevented a more detailed examination of procedural performance across institutions.

It is also worth noting that the arbitration sector in the GCC is undergoing rapid changes, both in terms of legislative reforms and the increasing use of digital tools. Therefore, several findings in the study reflect the situation as it stood up to 2025 and may evolve with new laws and institutional developments.

Given that the researcher lives and works in the UAE and is professionally involved in the construction and dispute-resolution field, there is a possibility that the surrounding professional environment influenced some interpretations, despite efforts to remain objective.

Finally, it was not possible to conduct a comprehensive comparison of arbitration centers due to inconsistent public reporting. Differences in administrative models, case-management practices, and digital readiness could therefore only be assessed to a limited extent within the scope of the study.

9. Conclusion

The conclusion reveals that arbitration in construction disputes across the GCC has grown noticeably stronger in recent years, becoming a more trusted and established method for resolving conflicts. This progress is evident in countries such as the UAE, Saudi Arabia, and Qatar, where legislative reforms have helped reinforce the legal framework and increase reliance on arbitration in both domestic and cross-border projects.

Despite these developments, several factors still limit the system's full effectiveness. The main challenges are procedural in nature, such as delays in forming arbitral tribunals, irregular timelines, and gaps in case management within certain institutions. These issues are largely institutional rather than legislative, highlighting the need for improved administrative systems and more consistent case management practices.

The study also notes that legal practices vary across GCC states, despite all of them adhering to major international conventions. Differences in judicial interpretation and the application of public policy rules can lead to inconsistent enforcement of arbitral awards. This reinforces the need for continued judicial training and greater harmonization to reduce uncertainty for users of arbitration.

Perceptions of arbitration also vary by the size of the company. Larger firms generally view arbitration as a reliable option, whereas many small and medium-sized enterprises see it as expensive or procedurally complex. This suggests that the system needs more flexible and cost-friendly procedures to ensure wider accessibility.

In terms of technology, some arbitration centers in the region have begun using digital platforms and virtual hearings, but adoption remains uneven. To fully benefit from digital transformation, the area will require additional investment in technological infrastructure, user training, and enhanced coordination among arbitration centers.

In summary, arbitration in the GCC is based on a solid legal foundation; however, further institutional and procedural improvements are necessary for the system to reach full maturity. Moving forward, deeper regional cooperation, stronger professional capacity, and more efficient processes will be essential to support the needs of the region's growing and dynamic construction sector.

10. Conflict of Interest

The author states that there is no conflict of interest.

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